

Ichneumonid parasitoids of the rice yellow borer in West Bengal, India

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The yellow stem borer population has often been low in the multiple rice cropping system on the alluvial soils of West Bengal. One reason for the low insect density may be the many parasitoids that attack yellow borer larvae or pupae. Parasitoids have also been found in sweep-net collections. The ichneumonid parasitoids found at the Chinsurah station, and identified after the type specimens by the Commonwealth

Parasitoid	Host stage	Time of collection	Remarks
<i>Temelucha philippinensis</i> (Ash.)	Larva and Pupa	Feb, Aug, and Dec	Also found in light trap
<i>Temelucha stangli</i> (Ash.)	Pupa	July	
<i>Isotima javensis</i> (Rohw.)	Larva and pupa	Feb, May, and Nov	
<i>Amauromorpha</i> sp.	Pupa	Apr	
<i>Trathala flavoorbitalis</i> (Cam.)	—	Aug to Nov	Only in sweep net
<i>Eriborus</i> sp.	—	Aug to Nov	Only in sweep net
<i>Xanthopimpla</i> spp.	—	Aug to Nov	Only in sweep net
<i>Goryphus mesoxanthus maculipennis</i> (Cam.)	—	Nov	Only in sweep net

institute of Biological Control, Bangalore, and by the key in IBP Handbook 14 are listed below. Further work on the host

range and relative abundance of the parasites is in progress. ■

Effects of spacing on rice hispa incidence

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A field trial was laid out in kharif 1978 to study the effect of spacing on rice insect incidence. Forty-five-day-old seedlings of PR106 were transplanted in 5- × 4-m plots at 3 spacings. Each spacing was replicated three times. Recommended agronomic practices were followed (120 kg N, 30 kg P₂O₅, and 30 kg K₂O/ha). The rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* was the predominant species attacking the crop. The damaged leaves on selected 10 hills from each plot were counted.

Although the differences in

Incidence of rice hispa in different spacings (mean of 9 observations). Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

Spacing (cm)	Damaged leaves ^a (av no./10 hills)				Mean
	20 DT	40 DT	60 DT	80 DT	
10 × 10	12.0 (3.43)	3.9 (1.96)	10.0 (3.15)	10.9 (3.28)	9.2
20 × 15	17.2 (4.14)	6.8 (2.56)	15.3 (3.80)	17.2 (4.13)	14.1
30 × 30	34.8 (5.79)	11.8 (0.42)	15.2 (3.90)	23.0 (4.70)	21.2
C.D. (P = 0.05)	(n.s.)	(1.39)	(n.s.)	(n.s.)	

^aFigures in parentheses arc/√n transformations. DT = days after transplanting. n.s. = nonsignificant.

hispa-damaged leaves in 3 spacings were significant only at 40 days after transplanting, the widely spaced plants were damaged more severely. There were 9.2, 14.1, and 21.2 hispa-damaged leaves per 10 hills in the 10- × 10-cm,

20- × 15-cm, and 30- × 30-cm spacing, respectively. The rice hispa prefers widely spaced plants probably because it lays eggs on leaf tips, which are better exposed in widely spaced plants. ■

Some new weed hosts of rice hispa recorded in India

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The rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera*, previously a minor rice pest in the Punjab, recently has become serious.

In 1978 kharif the weed flora at the Kapurthala Rice Research Station was intensively surveyed to determine if they serve as food plants for rice hispa. Adult hispa beetles were found on some common Gramineae weeds such as

Echinochloa crus-galli, *E. colona*, *Paspalum distichum*, and *Cynodon dactylon*. *E. crus-galli* and *E. colona* were generally found in and around rice fields, but *P. distichum* and *C. dactylon* were found mostly on bunds around the fields. The leaves of the attacked plants showed characteristic hispa feeding injury. There were, on the average, 29, 12, 12, and 11 adult beetles/10 plants on *E. crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *P. distichum*, and *C. dactylon*, respectively.

E. crus-galli, *P. distichum*, and *C. dactylon* are new additions to the list of weeds known to host the rice hispa in India. ■

Rice green leafhopper susceptibility to vamidothion in central Taiwan

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Rice green leafhoppers (GLH) collected at 5 locations within a 30-km² area in central Taiwan were tested by topical application for susceptibility to vamidothion, an organophosphorus insecticide for GLH control in Taiwan. Populations from two locations (A and E,